

Food Culture Practices for Wild Oyster Mushroom by tribal's of Nandurbar District

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Abstract

Fungi are the most important components of biotic cycle and act a key role in decompositions processes. This group of kingdoms consist of Mushrooms which can be edible and its mushroom traditional knowledge presents among tribes and their communities across the world. The current work is based on the collection, identifications and searching of a wild edible variety of Oyster mushrooms among tribes from Nandurbar district. *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Jacq.) to be found and recorded with recipes procedure as a wild edible mushrooms species of the tribes and these local area in rainy seasons.

Keywords: *Pleurotus ostreatus, Mushroom, Oyster, Fungi, Edible, Tribal's and Nandurbar district.*

Introduction

Kingdom fungi are represent the greatest eukaryotic diversity on earth and have been for a long time the primary decomposers of lignocellulolytic substrates (Floudas *et al.*, 2012) and the main keepers of great carbon storages in soil and dead organic material. As per Hawksworth (2001) diversity of fungi is estimated of approximately 1.5 million species worldwide. Ethnomycology is the study of wild macro fungi in folklore and rituals, from prehistoric times to that time (Ajith TA and Janardhanan KK 2013 and Charaya and Mehrotra, 1999) with their morphometric identification by tribe along with their documentation and indigenous knowledge regarding their uses as food has been recorded (Charaya and Mehrotra, 1999).

Mushrooms are one of the most important components of the forest ecosystem and grow generally in rainy season. Mushrooms are enriched in various bioactive substances like antibacterial, antiviral, antiparasitic, antifungal, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiproliferative, anticancer, hypocholesteromic, hepato-protective compounds (Ajith TA and Janardhanan KK 2003). Wild mushrooms are one of the important natural sources of food and income for many indigenous communities across

the world (Semwal *et al.*, 2014). Traditional or indigenous knowledge generally embedded in the cultural practices of regional or local communities based on the accumulation of empirical observations and interactions with the environment (Adhikari *et al.*, 2005 and Boa 2004). Moreover, there are records for use of mushrooms as food and medicine in India in the ancient treatise Charaka Samhita (3000 ± 500 BC). Since earliest times, mushrooms considered as a special kind of food (Adhikari *et al.*, 2005 and Boa 2004).

Traditional knowledge exists worldwide in most of the communities covering areas of health, agriculture and natural resource (Chang ST, Buswell JA 1996). The pattern of tribal life has not much changed since time immemorial. In the dense deep and remote forest area, nature is so kind that for thousands of years it has been possible for these tribal to get nutritious wild food gathering. A variety of natural products provide them a balanced diet which can be novel for modern world. Tribal mostly eat vegetables, which grow as wild weeds for their food. In times of scarcity, people are mostly dependent upon various species of wild plants (Kumar *et al.*, 2014 and Panda MK, Tayung K 2015).

Materials and Methods

In the present study field surveys was conducted in Nandurbar districts among different tribal groups in villages and forest during 2015 to 2016. The main features were observed and recorded that is about food cultures practice of mushrooms from forest. The current data was accrued through discussions and interviews with aged tribal and women who know to cook Mushrooms food. Type of food, materials used, processing etc various recorded about wild mushroom food with live photographs (Patil.M.B., 2009 and Patil & Deore 2012).

Result and Discussion

Study Area: Nandurbar District is a part of the Deccan plateau is situated in the Northern part of the Maharashtra State, with an area of 5034.23 sq. km. between 21⁰ N to 21.32⁰ N latitudes and 73.34⁰ E to 74.31⁰ E longitudes. It lies in the Valley of Tapi River and Satpuda mountains. The district can be divided into hilly tracts and undulating plain areas. Very small part of Narmada basin is towards

the west The Bhils, Gamits, Pasvis, Pawaras, Tadavi, Valvis and Vasaves are the various ethnic groups of the tribal people inhabit in the hilly region of Nandurbar district.

The tribes of various ethnic groups have their own dialect viz. Pavari, Mavchi, Bhili, Kokani etc. as mentioned earlier. Satpuda hill ranges and Tapi river basin form two distinct agroclimatic zones in the district. Part of the district is a fertile river basin where people practice agriculture and reap rich harvests. But the other part of the district is formed of difficult and unapproachable hilly terrain (Patil, 2009).

The climate here is dry, hot with scanty rain fall. People inhabiting this dry land region are ethnic groups. Their interaction with the civilized and developed societies of the other part of the district is very less. The ethnic groups interact mostly with their natural surroundings i.e. the deciduous forest. They developed their own life styles to cope with their Problems of food, nutrition, health and housing (Sharma TC 2010).

Observations: During the multiple field visits it was recorded that most of forest of Satpuda hills of Nandurbar district shows presence of wild species of mushrooms at rainy seasons. Among all these mushrooms' the most preferable for making food by locals tribes is *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Jacq.) Kummer commonly called as oyster mushroom. The identification has been done in laboratory with standard mycological flora.

Taxonomic Classification:

Domain: Eukaryota

Kingdom: Fungi

Phylum: Basidiomycota

Subphylum: Agaricomycotina

Class: Agaricomycetes

Subclass: Agaricomycetidae

Order: Agaricales

Family: Pleurotaceae

Genus: *Pleurotus*

Species: *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Tribal's of these areas are collected the Oyster from open forest. Some recipes are required dry Oyster were some other formulations are of fresh Oyster species. The performing procedure were recorded as per in photographs for making curry of mushrooms. Studies have indicated that oyster wild edible mushrooms are important sources of food (Boa E 2004). Purakayastha and Chandra have reported 283 edible species from India, out of which some are cultivated (Purakayastha RP and Chandra A 1985). Mushrooms have good ingredient of gourmet cuisine; chiefly, for their particular flavor and various traditional practices. It observes that their traditional processing and cooking knowledge determine the edibility of mushroom as a safe food (Panda MK, Tayung K 2015).

Conclusion

The present study revealed that the native tribal of Nandurbar district area can easily used wild Oyster mushroom as their food materials and have rich traditional knowledge regarding the utilization of wild mushrooms. The tribal inhabitants of this region use mushrooms mainly as food and few for medicinal purposes (Boa 2004). In monsoon period, local tribal's usually hunt for mushrooms along with other non-timber forest products in groups of 5-10 peoples preferably male belonging to the same family or community.

Fig: Steps of processing for wild edible Oyster Mushroom

It was noticed that traditional knowledge about the ethnomedicinal uses of wild mushrooms was generally confined to elderly aged persons of the villages. The mode of preparation and dose of administration were determined by local traditional healers (vernacularly known as ‘Vaidya’). There are some indigenous beliefs on the mushroom collection, consumption, and utilization. Incidence of mushroom poisoning was rare among the studied tribal communities. They have very distinct knowledge about poisonous mushrooms which are very similar in morphological appearance to edible species and may even occur in the same habitat.

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